

R for Psychologists - part II

ggplotting and long data

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It's been a very long time since I wrote anything. Life has been unexpectedly overwhelming for a period, still is I guess, but one musters on. I'm sitting in old town Fredrikstad while my cat is getting some tests at the vets', so I finally get some time and want to write something here. And we will continue with some R for Psychologists.

In my first R for Psychologists post we really dove into it. I very quickly covered getting SPSS data into R, doing some data wrangling (altering the data), plotting, and running a simple linear model. That was really quite the mountful of topics to cover. In this part, I'll take you more through plotting. You might think that is a weird place to dive into more, but there are perfectly good reasons for it (aside from me loving to make pretty plots). Plotting in R through `ggplot2` really is a way to get to understand how to organise and alter data in R to suit your needs. Getting data into the correct shape, with variables correctly made in to numerics, categorical (factors) etc. is very important. Not only does it affect how your plots end up, but will also dictate how your analyses work out. Just as in SPSS, data need to have the correct `types` or `classes` in order for the analyses to work correctly.

Let's start by opening the R-project we started with last time. If you have not been working in R since the last tutorial, you should be able to open RStudio, and our project will open immediately, and your script from last time should already be ready for you to work with. Otherwise, either navigate to the folder where your project was made and click on the `Rproj`-file, or in the top right corner of RStudio, click the drop-down menu next to the R-project icon and select the `R-start` project.

Our script from last time should look something like this:

```
library(rio)
library(tidyverse)

# Start with importing the data
eData = rio::import("SPSS/experim.sav") %>%
  # then recode sex to Male and Female
  mutate(
    sex = factor(sex, labels=c("Male", "Female")),
    id = factor(id))

# Gather depression variables into a tall depression data format.
eData_tall = eData %>%
  gather(time, depress, c("depress1", "depress2", "depress3")) %>%
  mutate(time = as.integer(gsub("[:alpha:]", "", time))) %>%
  arrange(id)

# Do a linear regression on depression over time
lm(depress~time, data=eData_tall) %>%
  broom::tidy()
```

```
# plot the regression
eData_tall %>%
  ggplot(aes(x=time, y=depress)) +
  geom_jitter() +
  geom_smooth(method="lm")
```

In this script we have already some both a plot (`ggplot`) and some data wrangling (`mutate`).

Ggplotting

`ggplot2` is a very powerful package for making plots. People who are used to plotting in SPSS or in base-R, find it hard to understand. I did to in the beginning, and it took me some time before I understood how it works and how to make my data into the shape that it needs for the plots to end up just as I like them. I know many researchers that will make simple plots in R or excel, and then get the plots into some vector program like Photoshop or Inkscape to make them exactly as they like. I did that too for a long time, but now I try to make sure my plots are reproducibly made through R, without the need for tweaking later so it looks nice and correct. Let's face it, that stuff takes a lot of time, and needs to be fixed with almost every co-author comment and review. So much time spent fixing.

But as I said last time, it takes time to get good enough in R to not need that step, and making the scripts also takes time. There are no quick-fix solutions, but I believe R makes the fixes faster, as they will be minor tweaks, or if new data comes in, just load the new data, and rerun, and presto all the plots are updated.

Anyway, let's get into it. Let's have a look at the plot from last time, at the end of our script.

```
# plot the regression
eData_tall %>%
  ggplot(aes(x=time, y=depress)) +
  geom_jitter() +
  geom_smooth(method="lm")

## `geom_smooth()` using formula 'y ~ x'
```


Alrighty, we have the individual data points for depression (y-axis) at each timepoint (x-axis) for all individuals as the scatter plot, and a regression-line fitted to that data. To reiterate what the code is doing: “Take `eData_tall`, plot with time on the x-axis, depress on the y-axis, create a scatter plot with a little bit of random noise, and add a regression line using a linear model.” Let’s break that down a little bit by looking at the data again.

```
eData_tall %>%
  glimpse()
```

```
## Rows: 90
## Columns: 17
## $ id      <fct> 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 2, 3, 3, 3, 4, 4, 4, 5, 5, 5, 6, 6, 6, 7, 7, ...
## $ sex     <fct> Male, ...
## $ age     <dbl> 19, 19, 19, 21, 21, 21, 30, 30, 30, 23, 23, 23, 26, 26, 26, ...
## $ group   <dbl> 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 2, 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 2, 1, 1, 1, 2, 2, 2, 1, 1, ...
## $ fost1   <dbl> 32, 32, 32, 37, 37, 37, 47, 47, 47, 50, 50, 50, 44, 44, 44, ...
## $ confid1 <dbl> 20, 20, 20, 29, 29, 29, 11, 11, 11, 15, 15, 15, 17, 17, 17, ...
## $ fost2   <dbl> 28, 28, 28, 36, 36, 36, 42, 42, 42, 48, 48, 48, 37, 37, 37, ...
## $ confid2 <dbl> 25, 25, 25, 30, 30, 30, 16, 16, 16, 16, 16, 16, 20, 20, 20, ...
## $ fost3   <dbl> 23, 23, 23, 34, 34, 34, 41, 41, 41, 45, 45, 45, 32, 32, 32, ...
## $ confid3 <dbl> 30, 30, 30, 34, 34, 34, 20, 20, 20, 14, 14, 14, 26, 26, 26, ...
## $ exam    <dbl> 82, 82, 82, 90, 90, 90, 60, 60, 60, 52, 52, 52, 70, 70, 70, ...
## $ mah_1   <dbl> 0.3469978, 0.3469978, 0.3469978, 10.2401804, 10.2401804, 10.2401804, ...
## $ DepT1gp2 <dbl> 0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, ...
## $ DepT2Gp2 <dbl> 0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, ...
## $ DepT3gp2 <dbl> 0, 0, 0, 1, 1, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, ...
```

```
## $ time      <int> 1, 2, 3, 1, 2, 3, 1, 2, 3, 1, 2, 3, 1, 2, 3, 1, 2, 3, 1, 2, ...
## $ depress   <dbl> 44, 43, 40, 50, 47, 45, 43, 43, 43, 44, 44, 40, 46, 47, 42, ...
```

So `time` is an *integer* with three values (1-3) and `depress` is a double precision number with a depression score. Again, notice how in the `id` column, the subject identifiers are repeated in three rows, last time we made this *long* dataset where participants had *as many rows as number of time observations*. This is a very convenient way of working with data, and while it might take a little time to get used to, it does make a lot of sense. When you have data repeating over time, the *same data* repeated over time, it is easier to get an overview of in long format so you don't need to scroll sideways and lose your navigation points (`id`) too easily.

Now, last time, we only made `depress` into long format. But technically, most of the data in this dataset is repeated, and thankfully named in such a way that it is quite easy for us to reshape the data. When we have done this, we can make some really nice plots too!

Reshape the data

We'll go back to the original `eData` file for this.

```
eData %>% glimpse()

## Rows: 30
## Columns: 18
## $ id      <fct> 4, 10, 9, 3, 12, 11, 6, 5, 8, 13, 14, 1, 15, 7, 2, 27, 25, 1...
## $ sex     <fct> Male, ...
## $ age     <dbl> 23, 21, 25, 30, 45, 22, 22, 26, 23, 21, 23, 19, 23, 19, 21, ...
## $ group   <dbl> 2, 2, 1, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 2, 1, 1, 1, 2, 1, ...
## $ fost1   <dbl> 50, 47, 44, 47, 46, 39, 32, 44, 40, 47, 38, 32, 39, 36, 37, ...
## $ confid1 <dbl> 15, 14, 12, 11, 16, 13, 21, 17, 22, 20, 28, 20, 21, 24, 29, ...
## $ depress1 <dbl> 44, 42, 40, 43, 44, 43, 37, 46, 37, 50, 39, 44, 47, 38, 50, ...
## $ fost2   <dbl> 48, 45, 39, 42, 45, 40, 33, 37, 40, 45, 37, 28, 35, 32, 36, ...
## $ confid2 <dbl> 16, 15, 18, 16, 16, 20, 22, 20, 23, 25, 27, 25, 26, 28, 30, ...
## $ depress2 <dbl> 44, 42, 40, 43, 45, 42, 36, 47, 37, 48, 36, 43, 47, 35, 47, ...
## $ fost3   <dbl> 45, 44, 36, 41, 43, 39, 32, 32, 40, 46, 32, 23, 35, 30, 34, ...
## $ confid3 <dbl> 14, 18, 19, 20, 20, 22, 23, 26, 26, 27, 29, 30, 30, 32, 34, ...
## $ depress3 <dbl> 40, 40, 38, 43, 43, 38, 35, 42, 35, 46, 34, 40, 47, 35, 45, ...
## $ exam    <dbl> 52, 55, 58, 60, 58, 62, 59, 70, 60, 70, 72, 82, 79, 80, 90, ...
## $ mah_1   <dbl> 0.5699842, 1.6594031, 3.5404715, 2.4542143, 0.9443036, 1.625...
## $ DepT1gp2 <dbl> 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 0, 1, 0, 1, 1, 0, 1, 0, 0, ...
## $ DepT2gp2 <dbl> 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0, ...
## $ DepT3gp2 <dbl> 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 1, 0, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0, 0, 0, 0, ...
```

Notice that in the dataset, all variables that are repeated have a number in their variable name, except `mah_1` which is not repeated, but we can work with that. This logic helps us a lot, as it will make it possible for us to wrangle the data into shape using that logic.

As we did last time, we will use the `gather` function from `tidyverse` to make the data long, and use the logic of numbers in the column names to help to get the data into shape.

```
eData %>%
  gather(colName, value, matches("[123]"))

## Warning: attributes are not identical across measure variables;
## they will be dropped

##   id  sex age group exam colName      value
## 1   4 Male 23    2   52  fost1 50.0000000
## 2  10 Male 21    2   55  fost1 47.0000000
## 3   9 Male 25    1   58  fost1 44.0000000
```

## 4	3	Male	30	1	60	fost1	47.0000000
## 5	12	Male	45	2	58	fost1	46.0000000
## 6	11	Male	22	1	62	fost1	39.0000000
## 7	6	Male	22	2	59	fost1	32.0000000
## 8	5	Male	26	1	70	fost1	44.0000000
## 9	8	Male	23	2	60	fost1	40.0000000
## 10	13	Male	21	1	70	fost1	47.0000000
## 11	14	Male	23	2	72	fost1	38.0000000
## 12	1	Male	19	1	82	fost1	32.0000000
## 13	15	Male	23	1	79	fost1	39.0000000
## 14	7	Male	19	1	80	fost1	36.0000000
## 15	2	Male	21	2	90	fost1	37.0000000
## 16	27	Female	20	1	56	fost1	41.0000000
## 17	25	Female	24	1	53	fost1	38.0000000
## 18	19	Female	27	1	59	fost1	42.0000000
## 19	18	Female	23	2	64	fost1	44.0000000
## 20	23	Female	22	1	63	fost1	32.0000000
## 21	21	Female	46	1	64	fost1	39.0000000
## 22	26	Female	19	2	63	fost1	42.0000000
## 23	29	Female	22	1	67	fost1	37.0000000
## 24	17	Female	37	1	71	fost1	41.0000000
## 25	20	Female	32	2	73	fost1	43.0000000
## 26	28	Female	30	2	80	fost1	46.0000000
## 27	22	Female	25	2	83	fost1	30.0000000
## 28	24	Female	21	2	85	fost1	33.0000000
## 29	16	Female	45	2	78	fost1	40.0000000
## 30	30	Female	21	2	84	fost1	39.0000000
## 31	4	Male	23	2	52	confid1	15.0000000
## 32	10	Male	21	2	55	confid1	14.0000000
## 33	9	Male	25	1	58	confid1	12.0000000
## 34	3	Male	30	1	60	confid1	11.0000000
## 35	12	Male	45	2	58	confid1	16.0000000
## 36	11	Male	22	1	62	confid1	13.0000000
## 37	6	Male	22	2	59	confid1	21.0000000
## 38	5	Male	26	1	70	confid1	17.0000000
## 39	8	Male	23	2	60	confid1	22.0000000
## 40	13	Male	21	1	70	confid1	20.0000000
## 41	14	Male	23	2	72	confid1	28.0000000
## 42	1	Male	19	1	82	confid1	20.0000000
## 43	15	Male	23	1	79	confid1	21.0000000
## 44	7	Male	19	1	80	confid1	24.0000000
## 45	2	Male	21	2	90	confid1	29.0000000
## 46	27	Female	20	1	56	confid1	16.0000000
## 47	25	Female	24	1	53	confid1	14.0000000
## 48	19	Female	27	1	59	confid1	15.0000000
## 49	18	Female	23	2	64	confid1	13.0000000
## 50	23	Female	22	1	63	confid1	22.0000000
## 51	21	Female	46	1	64	confid1	21.0000000
## 52	26	Female	19	2	63	confid1	13.0000000
## 53	29	Female	22	1	67	confid1	28.0000000
## 54	17	Female	37	1	71	confid1	29.0000000
## 55	20	Female	32	2	73	confid1	17.0000000
## 56	28	Female	30	2	80	confid1	20.0000000
## 57	22	Female	25	2	83	confid1	24.0000000

## 58	24	Female	21	2	85	confid1	12.0000000
## 59	16	Female	45	2	78	confid1	22.0000000
## 60	30	Female	21	2	84	confid1	21.0000000
## 61	4	Male	23	2	52	depress1	44.0000000
## 62	10	Male	21	2	55	depress1	42.0000000
## 63	9	Male	25	1	58	depress1	40.0000000
## 64	3	Male	30	1	60	depress1	43.0000000
## 65	12	Male	45	2	58	depress1	44.0000000
## 66	11	Male	22	1	62	depress1	43.0000000
## 67	6	Male	22	2	59	depress1	37.0000000
## 68	5	Male	26	1	70	depress1	46.0000000
## 69	8	Male	23	2	60	depress1	37.0000000
## 70	13	Male	21	1	70	depress1	50.0000000
## 71	14	Male	23	2	72	depress1	39.0000000
## 72	1	Male	19	1	82	depress1	44.0000000
## 73	15	Male	23	1	79	depress1	47.0000000
## 74	7	Male	19	1	80	depress1	38.0000000
## 75	2	Male	21	2	90	depress1	50.0000000
## 76	27	Female	20	1	56	depress1	45.0000000
## 77	25	Female	24	1	53	depress1	42.0000000
## 78	19	Female	27	1	59	depress1	49.0000000
## 79	18	Female	23	2	64	depress1	39.0000000
## 80	23	Female	22	1	63	depress1	39.0000000
## 81	21	Female	46	1	64	depress1	44.0000000
## 82	26	Female	19	2	63	depress1	43.0000000
## 83	29	Female	22	1	67	depress1	33.0000000
## 84	17	Female	37	1	71	depress1	39.0000000
## 85	20	Female	32	2	73	depress1	47.0000000
## 86	28	Female	30	2	80	depress1	38.0000000
## 87	22	Female	25	2	83	depress1	45.0000000
## 88	24	Female	21	2	85	depress1	50.0000000
## 89	16	Female	45	2	78	depress1	45.0000000
## 90	30	Female	21	2	84	depress1	34.0000000
## 91	4	Male	23	2	52	fost2	48.0000000
## 92	10	Male	21	2	55	fost2	45.0000000
## 93	9	Male	25	1	58	fost2	39.0000000
## 94	3	Male	30	1	60	fost2	42.0000000
## 95	12	Male	45	2	58	fost2	45.0000000
## 96	11	Male	22	1	62	fost2	40.0000000
## 97	6	Male	22	2	59	fost2	33.0000000
## 98	5	Male	26	1	70	fost2	37.0000000
## 99	8	Male	23	2	60	fost2	40.0000000
## 100	13	Male	21	1	70	fost2	45.0000000
## 101	14	Male	23	2	72	fost2	37.0000000
## 102	1	Male	19	1	82	fost2	28.0000000
## 103	15	Male	23	1	79	fost2	35.0000000
## 104	7	Male	19	1	80	fost2	32.0000000
## 105	2	Male	21	2	90	fost2	36.0000000
## 106	27	Female	20	1	56	fost2	40.0000000
## 107	25	Female	24	1	53	fost2	37.0000000
## 108	19	Female	27	1	59	fost2	41.0000000
## 109	18	Female	23	2	64	fost2	39.0000000
## 110	23	Female	22	1	63	fost2	31.0000000
## 111	21	Female	46	1	64	fost2	40.0000000

##	112	26	Female	19	2	63	fost2	38.0000000
##	113	29	Female	22	1	67	fost2	38.0000000
##	114	17	Female	37	1	71	fost2	40.0000000
##	115	20	Female	32	2	73	fost2	36.0000000
##	116	28	Female	30	2	80	fost2	40.0000000
##	117	22	Female	25	2	83	fost2	28.0000000
##	118	24	Female	21	2	85	fost2	29.0000000
##	119	16	Female	45	2	78	fost2	30.0000000
##	120	30	Female	21	2	84	fost2	36.0000000
##	121	4	Male	23	2	52	confid2	16.0000000
##	122	10	Male	21	2	55	confid2	15.0000000
##	123	9	Male	25	1	58	confid2	18.0000000
##	124	3	Male	30	1	60	confid2	16.0000000
##	125	12	Male	45	2	58	confid2	16.0000000
##	126	11	Male	22	1	62	confid2	20.0000000
##	127	6	Male	22	2	59	confid2	22.0000000
##	128	5	Male	26	1	70	confid2	20.0000000
##	129	8	Male	23	2	60	confid2	23.0000000
##	130	13	Male	21	1	70	confid2	25.0000000
##	131	14	Male	23	2	72	confid2	27.0000000
##	132	1	Male	19	1	82	confid2	25.0000000
##	133	15	Male	23	1	79	confid2	26.0000000
##	134	7	Male	19	1	80	confid2	28.0000000
##	135	2	Male	21	2	90	confid2	30.0000000
##	136	27	Female	20	1	56	confid2	14.0000000
##	137	25	Female	24	1	53	confid2	14.0000000
##	138	19	Female	27	1	59	confid2	13.0000000
##	139	18	Female	23	2	64	confid2	20.0000000
##	140	23	Female	22	1	63	confid2	18.0000000
##	141	21	Female	46	1	64	confid2	19.0000000
##	142	26	Female	19	2	63	confid2	20.0000000
##	143	29	Female	22	1	67	confid2	22.0000000
##	144	17	Female	37	1	71	confid2	22.0000000
##	145	20	Female	32	2	73	confid2	26.0000000
##	146	28	Female	30	2	80	confid2	28.0000000
##	147	22	Female	25	2	83	confid2	28.0000000
##	148	24	Female	21	2	85	confid2	20.0000000
##	149	16	Female	45	2	78	confid2	35.0000000
##	150	30	Female	21	2	84	confid2	30.0000000
##	151	4	Male	23	2	52	depress2	44.0000000
##	152	10	Male	21	2	55	depress2	42.0000000
##	153	9	Male	25	1	58	depress2	40.0000000
##	154	3	Male	30	1	60	depress2	43.0000000
##	155	12	Male	45	2	58	depress2	45.0000000
##	156	11	Male	22	1	62	depress2	42.0000000
##	157	6	Male	22	2	59	depress2	36.0000000
##	158	5	Male	26	1	70	depress2	47.0000000
##	159	8	Male	23	2	60	depress2	37.0000000
##	160	13	Male	21	1	70	depress2	48.0000000
##	161	14	Male	23	2	72	depress2	36.0000000
##	162	1	Male	19	1	82	depress2	43.0000000
##	163	15	Male	23	1	79	depress2	47.0000000
##	164	7	Male	19	1	80	depress2	35.0000000
##	165	2	Male	21	2	90	depress2	47.0000000

##	166	27	Female	20	1	56	depress2	44.0000000
##	167	25	Female	24	1	53	depress2	40.0000000
##	168	19	Female	27	1	59	depress2	49.0000000
##	169	18	Female	23	2	64	depress2	30.0000000
##	170	23	Female	22	1	63	depress2	38.0000000
##	171	21	Female	46	1	64	depress2	44.0000000
##	172	26	Female	19	2	63	depress2	39.0000000
##	173	29	Female	22	1	67	depress2	33.0000000
##	174	17	Female	37	1	71	depress2	40.0000000
##	175	20	Female	32	2	73	depress2	45.0000000
##	176	28	Female	30	2	80	depress2	30.0000000
##	177	22	Female	25	2	83	depress2	40.0000000
##	178	24	Female	21	2	85	depress2	48.0000000
##	179	16	Female	45	2	78	depress2	40.0000000
##	180	30	Female	21	2	84	depress2	30.0000000
##	181	4	Male	23	2	52	fost3	45.0000000
##	182	10	Male	21	2	55	fost3	44.0000000
##	183	9	Male	25	1	58	fost3	36.0000000
##	184	3	Male	30	1	60	fost3	41.0000000
##	185	12	Male	45	2	58	fost3	43.0000000
##	186	11	Male	22	1	62	fost3	39.0000000
##	187	6	Male	22	2	59	fost3	32.0000000
##	188	5	Male	26	1	70	fost3	32.0000000
##	189	8	Male	23	2	60	fost3	40.0000000
##	190	13	Male	21	1	70	fost3	46.0000000
##	191	14	Male	23	2	72	fost3	32.0000000
##	192	1	Male	19	1	82	fost3	23.0000000
##	193	15	Male	23	1	79	fost3	35.0000000
##	194	7	Male	19	1	80	fost3	30.0000000
##	195	2	Male	21	2	90	fost3	34.0000000
##	196	27	Female	20	1	56	fost3	38.0000000
##	197	25	Female	24	1	53	fost3	35.0000000
##	198	19	Female	27	1	59	fost3	40.0000000
##	199	18	Female	23	2	64	fost3	34.0000000
##	200	23	Female	22	1	63	fost3	32.0000000
##	201	21	Female	46	1	64	fost3	38.0000000
##	202	26	Female	19	2	63	fost3	36.0000000
##	203	29	Female	22	1	67	fost3	36.0000000
##	204	17	Female	37	1	71	fost3	40.0000000
##	205	20	Female	32	2	73	fost3	34.0000000
##	206	28	Female	30	2	80	fost3	37.0000000
##	207	22	Female	25	2	83	fost3	25.0000000
##	208	24	Female	21	2	85	fost3	25.0000000
##	209	16	Female	45	2	78	fost3	25.0000000
##	210	30	Female	21	2	84	fost3	30.0000000
##	211	4	Male	23	2	52	confid3	14.0000000
##	212	10	Male	21	2	55	confid3	18.0000000
##	213	9	Male	25	1	58	confid3	19.0000000
##	214	3	Male	30	1	60	confid3	20.0000000
##	215	12	Male	45	2	58	confid3	20.0000000
##	216	11	Male	22	1	62	confid3	22.0000000
##	217	6	Male	22	2	59	confid3	23.0000000
##	218	5	Male	26	1	70	confid3	26.0000000
##	219	8	Male	23	2	60	confid3	26.0000000

##	220	13	Male	21	1	70	confid3	27.0000000
##	221	14	Male	23	2	72	confid3	29.0000000
##	222	1	Male	19	1	82	confid3	30.0000000
##	223	15	Male	23	1	79	confid3	30.0000000
##	224	7	Male	19	1	80	confid3	32.0000000
##	225	2	Male	21	2	90	confid3	34.0000000
##	226	27	Female	20	1	56	confid3	18.0000000
##	227	25	Female	24	1	53	confid3	19.0000000
##	228	19	Female	27	1	59	confid3	20.0000000
##	229	18	Female	23	2	64	confid3	22.0000000
##	230	23	Female	22	1	63	confid3	22.0000000
##	231	21	Female	46	1	64	confid3	23.0000000
##	232	26	Female	19	2	63	confid3	23.0000000
##	233	29	Female	22	1	67	confid3	26.0000000
##	234	17	Female	37	1	71	confid3	27.0000000
##	235	20	Female	32	2	73	confid3	28.0000000
##	236	28	Female	30	2	80	confid3	29.0000000
##	237	22	Female	25	2	83	confid3	30.0000000
##	238	24	Female	21	2	85	confid3	30.0000000
##	239	16	Female	45	2	78	confid3	32.0000000
##	240	30	Female	21	2	84	confid3	32.0000000
##	241	4	Male	23	2	52	depress3	40.0000000
##	242	10	Male	21	2	55	depress3	40.0000000
##	243	9	Male	25	1	58	depress3	38.0000000
##	244	3	Male	30	1	60	depress3	43.0000000
##	245	12	Male	45	2	58	depress3	43.0000000
##	246	11	Male	22	1	62	depress3	38.0000000
##	247	6	Male	22	2	59	depress3	35.0000000
##	248	5	Male	26	1	70	depress3	42.0000000
##	249	8	Male	23	2	60	depress3	35.0000000
##	250	13	Male	21	1	70	depress3	46.0000000
##	251	14	Male	23	2	72	depress3	34.0000000
##	252	1	Male	19	1	82	depress3	40.0000000
##	253	15	Male	23	1	79	depress3	47.0000000
##	254	7	Male	19	1	80	depress3	35.0000000
##	255	2	Male	21	2	90	depress3	45.0000000
##	256	27	Female	20	1	56	depress3	40.0000000
##	257	25	Female	24	1	53	depress3	39.0000000
##	258	19	Female	27	1	59	depress3	44.0000000
##	259	18	Female	23	2	64	depress3	30.0000000
##	260	23	Female	22	1	63	depress3	36.0000000
##	261	21	Female	46	1	64	depress3	44.0000000
##	262	26	Female	19	2	63	depress3	37.0000000
##	263	29	Female	22	1	67	depress3	32.0000000
##	264	17	Female	37	1	71	depress3	40.0000000
##	265	20	Female	32	2	73	depress3	42.0000000
##	266	28	Female	30	2	80	depress3	29.0000000
##	267	22	Female	25	2	83	depress3	38.0000000
##	268	24	Female	21	2	85	depress3	50.0000000
##	269	16	Female	45	2	78	depress3	42.0000000
##	270	30	Female	21	2	84	depress3	32.0000000
##	271	4	Male	23	2	52	mah_1	0.5699842
##	272	10	Male	21	2	55	mah_1	1.6594031
##	273	9	Male	25	1	58	mah_1	3.5404715

##	274	3	Male	30	1	60	mah_1	2.4542143
##	275	12	Male	45	2	58	mah_1	0.9443036
##	276	11	Male	22	1	62	mah_1	1.6257058
##	277	6	Male	22	2	59	mah_1	4.1744717
##	278	5	Male	26	1	70	mah_1	1.0261059
##	279	8	Male	23	2	60	mah_1	1.7053103
##	280	13	Male	21	1	70	mah_1	3.0873214
##	281	14	Male	23	2	72	mah_1	2.9140163
##	282	1	Male	19	1	82	mah_1	0.3469978
##	283	15	Male	23	1	79	mah_1	1.5886241
##	284	7	Male	19	1	80	mah_1	1.5076582
##	285	2	Male	21	2	90	mah_1	10.2401804
##	286	27	Female	20	1	56	mah_1	1.1776467
##	287	25	Female	24	1	53	mah_1	1.0564668
##	288	19	Female	27	1	59	mah_1	3.8748910
##	289	18	Female	23	2	64	mah_1	2.7101641
##	290	23	Female	22	1	63	mah_1	3.5488594
##	291	21	Female	46	1	64	mah_1	0.5007192
##	292	26	Female	19	2	63	mah_1	1.4739118
##	293	29	Female	22	1	67	mah_1	9.1295758
##	294	17	Female	37	1	71	mah_1	6.2065842
##	295	20	Female	32	2	73	mah_1	1.7190981
##	296	28	Female	30	2	80	mah_1	1.5015533
##	297	22	Female	25	2	83	mah_1	1.9240376
##	298	24	Female	21	2	85	mah_1	7.5576411
##	299	16	Female	45	2	78	mah_1	1.1884922
##	300	30	Female	21	2	84	mah_1	6.0455901
##	301	4	Male	23	2	52	DepT1gp2	0.0000000
##	302	10	Male	21	2	55	DepT1gp2	0.0000000
##	303	9	Male	25	1	58	DepT1gp2	0.0000000
##	304	3	Male	30	1	60	DepT1gp2	0.0000000
##	305	12	Male	45	2	58	DepT1gp2	0.0000000
##	306	11	Male	22	1	62	DepT1gp2	0.0000000
##	307	6	Male	22	2	59	DepT1gp2	0.0000000
##	308	5	Male	26	1	70	DepT1gp2	1.0000000
##	309	8	Male	23	2	60	DepT1gp2	0.0000000
##	310	13	Male	21	1	70	DepT1gp2	1.0000000
##	311	14	Male	23	2	72	DepT1gp2	0.0000000
##	312	1	Male	19	1	82	DepT1gp2	0.0000000
##	313	15	Male	23	1	79	DepT1gp2	1.0000000
##	314	7	Male	19	1	80	DepT1gp2	0.0000000
##	315	2	Male	21	2	90	DepT1gp2	1.0000000
##	316	27	Female	20	1	56	DepT1gp2	1.0000000
##	317	25	Female	24	1	53	DepT1gp2	0.0000000
##	318	19	Female	27	1	59	DepT1gp2	1.0000000
##	319	18	Female	23	2	64	DepT1gp2	0.0000000
##	320	23	Female	22	1	63	DepT1gp2	0.0000000
##	321	21	Female	46	1	64	DepT1gp2	0.0000000
##	322	26	Female	19	2	63	DepT1gp2	0.0000000
##	323	29	Female	22	1	67	DepT1gp2	0.0000000
##	324	17	Female	37	1	71	DepT1gp2	0.0000000
##	325	20	Female	32	2	73	DepT1gp2	1.0000000
##	326	28	Female	30	2	80	DepT1gp2	0.0000000
##	327	22	Female	25	2	83	DepT1gp2	1.0000000

##	328	24	Female	21	2	85	DepT1gp2	1.0000000
##	329	16	Female	45	2	78	DepT1gp2	1.0000000
##	330	30	Female	21	2	84	DepT1gp2	0.0000000
##	331	4	Male	23	2	52	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	332	10	Male	21	2	55	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	333	9	Male	25	1	58	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	334	3	Male	30	1	60	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	335	12	Male	45	2	58	DepT2Gp2	1.0000000
##	336	11	Male	22	1	62	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	337	6	Male	22	2	59	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	338	5	Male	26	1	70	DepT2Gp2	1.0000000
##	339	8	Male	23	2	60	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	340	13	Male	21	1	70	DepT2Gp2	1.0000000
##	341	14	Male	23	2	72	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	342	1	Male	19	1	82	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	343	15	Male	23	1	79	DepT2Gp2	1.0000000
##	344	7	Male	19	1	80	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	345	2	Male	21	2	90	DepT2Gp2	1.0000000
##	346	27	Female	20	1	56	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	347	25	Female	24	1	53	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	348	19	Female	27	1	59	DepT2Gp2	1.0000000
##	349	18	Female	23	2	64	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	350	23	Female	22	1	63	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	351	21	Female	46	1	64	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	352	26	Female	19	2	63	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	353	29	Female	22	1	67	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	354	17	Female	37	1	71	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	355	20	Female	32	2	73	DepT2Gp2	1.0000000
##	356	28	Female	30	2	80	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	357	22	Female	25	2	83	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	358	24	Female	21	2	85	DepT2Gp2	1.0000000
##	359	16	Female	45	2	78	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	360	30	Female	21	2	84	DepT2Gp2	0.0000000
##	361	4	Male	23	2	52	DepT3gp2	0.0000000
##	362	10	Male	21	2	55	DepT3gp2	0.0000000
##	363	9	Male	25	1	58	DepT3gp2	0.0000000
##	364	3	Male	30	1	60	DepT3gp2	0.0000000
##	365	12	Male	45	2	58	DepT3gp2	0.0000000
##	366	11	Male	22	1	62	DepT3gp2	0.0000000
##	367	6	Male	22	2	59	DepT3gp2	0.0000000
##	368	5	Male	26	1	70	DepT3gp2	0.0000000
##	369	8	Male	23	2	60	DepT3gp2	0.0000000
##	370	13	Male	21	1	70	DepT3gp2	1.0000000
##	371	14	Male	23	2	72	DepT3gp2	0.0000000
##	372	1	Male	19	1	82	DepT3gp2	0.0000000
##	373	15	Male	23	1	79	DepT3gp2	1.0000000
##	374	7	Male	19	1	80	DepT3gp2	0.0000000
##	375	2	Male	21	2	90	DepT3gp2	1.0000000
##	376	27	Female	20	1	56	DepT3gp2	0.0000000
##	377	25	Female	24	1	53	DepT3gp2	0.0000000
##	378	19	Female	27	1	59	DepT3gp2	0.0000000
##	379	18	Female	23	2	64	DepT3gp2	0.0000000
##	380	23	Female	22	1	63	DepT3gp2	0.0000000
##	381	21	Female	46	1	64	DepT3gp2	0.0000000

```
## 382 26 Female 19 2 63 DepT3gp2 0.0000000
## 383 29 Female 22 1 67 DepT3gp2 0.0000000
## 384 17 Female 37 1 71 DepT3gp2 0.0000000
## 385 20 Female 32 2 73 DepT3gp2 0.0000000
## 386 28 Female 30 2 80 DepT3gp2 0.0000000
## 387 22 Female 25 2 83 DepT3gp2 0.0000000
## 388 24 Female 21 2 85 DepT3gp2 1.0000000
## 389 16 Female 45 2 78 DepT3gp2 0.0000000
## 390 30 Female 21 2 84 DepT3gp2 0.0000000
```

As I usually do when I work, I start by running commands in my console, *without* saving the output (i.e. putting something to the left of an = sign of that command), so I can make sure the commands are doing what I expect. Let's face it, we'll never be computers, you will rarely write a command that does everything you want in one go.

In this case I said "Take *eData*, gather all variables that matches with 1,2 or 3 in their variable name, and place all the variable names into a column named *colName* and the values of those columns into a variable called *value*"

That was step one, now we want to make sure we have one column with the names of the columns *without* the numbers in one variable, and the numbers into a column named *time*. We are going to use *mutate* for that in this case.

```
eData %>%
  gather(colName, value, matches("[123]")) %>%
  mutate(time = parse_number(colName),
         colName = gsub("[:digit:]", "", colName))
```

```
## Warning: attributes are not identical across measure variables;
## they will be dropped
```

```
##   id  sex age group exam colName  value time
## 1   4 Male 23  2  52   fost 50.0000000  1
## 2  10 Male 21  2  55   fost 47.0000000  1
## 3   9 Male 25  1  58   fost 44.0000000  1
## 4   3 Male 30  1  60   fost 47.0000000  1
## 5  12 Male 45  2  58   fost 46.0000000  1
## 6  11 Male 22  1  62   fost 39.0000000  1
## 7   6 Male 22  2  59   fost 32.0000000  1
## 8   5 Male 26  1  70   fost 44.0000000  1
## 9   8 Male 23  2  60   fost 40.0000000  1
## 10 13 Male 21  1  70   fost 47.0000000  1
## 11 14 Male 23  2  72   fost 38.0000000  1
## 12  1 Male 19  1  82   fost 32.0000000  1
## 13 15 Male 23  1  79   fost 39.0000000  1
## 14  7 Male 19  1  80   fost 36.0000000  1
## 15  2 Male 21  2  90   fost 37.0000000  1
## 16 27 Female 20  1  56   fost 41.0000000  1
## 17 25 Female 24  1  53   fost 38.0000000  1
## 18 19 Female 27  1  59   fost 42.0000000  1
## 19 18 Female 23  2  64   fost 44.0000000  1
## 20 23 Female 22  1  63   fost 32.0000000  1
## 21 21 Female 46  1  64   fost 39.0000000  1
## 22 26 Female 19  2  63   fost 42.0000000  1
## 23 29 Female 22  1  67   fost 37.0000000  1
## 24 17 Female 37  1  71   fost 41.0000000  1
## 25 20 Female 32  2  73   fost 43.0000000  1
```

##	26	28	Female	30	2	80	fost	46.0000000	1
##	27	22	Female	25	2	83	fost	30.0000000	1
##	28	24	Female	21	2	85	fost	33.0000000	1
##	29	16	Female	45	2	78	fost	40.0000000	1
##	30	30	Female	21	2	84	fost	39.0000000	1
##	31	4	Male	23	2	52	confid	15.0000000	1
##	32	10	Male	21	2	55	confid	14.0000000	1
##	33	9	Male	25	1	58	confid	12.0000000	1
##	34	3	Male	30	1	60	confid	11.0000000	1
##	35	12	Male	45	2	58	confid	16.0000000	1
##	36	11	Male	22	1	62	confid	13.0000000	1
##	37	6	Male	22	2	59	confid	21.0000000	1
##	38	5	Male	26	1	70	confid	17.0000000	1
##	39	8	Male	23	2	60	confid	22.0000000	1
##	40	13	Male	21	1	70	confid	20.0000000	1
##	41	14	Male	23	2	72	confid	28.0000000	1
##	42	1	Male	19	1	82	confid	20.0000000	1
##	43	15	Male	23	1	79	confid	21.0000000	1
##	44	7	Male	19	1	80	confid	24.0000000	1
##	45	2	Male	21	2	90	confid	29.0000000	1
##	46	27	Female	20	1	56	confid	16.0000000	1
##	47	25	Female	24	1	53	confid	14.0000000	1
##	48	19	Female	27	1	59	confid	15.0000000	1
##	49	18	Female	23	2	64	confid	13.0000000	1
##	50	23	Female	22	1	63	confid	22.0000000	1
##	51	21	Female	46	1	64	confid	21.0000000	1
##	52	26	Female	19	2	63	confid	13.0000000	1
##	53	29	Female	22	1	67	confid	28.0000000	1
##	54	17	Female	37	1	71	confid	29.0000000	1
##	55	20	Female	32	2	73	confid	17.0000000	1
##	56	28	Female	30	2	80	confid	20.0000000	1
##	57	22	Female	25	2	83	confid	24.0000000	1
##	58	24	Female	21	2	85	confid	12.0000000	1
##	59	16	Female	45	2	78	confid	22.0000000	1
##	60	30	Female	21	2	84	confid	21.0000000	1
##	61	4	Male	23	2	52	depress	44.0000000	1
##	62	10	Male	21	2	55	depress	42.0000000	1
##	63	9	Male	25	1	58	depress	40.0000000	1
##	64	3	Male	30	1	60	depress	43.0000000	1
##	65	12	Male	45	2	58	depress	44.0000000	1
##	66	11	Male	22	1	62	depress	43.0000000	1
##	67	6	Male	22	2	59	depress	37.0000000	1
##	68	5	Male	26	1	70	depress	46.0000000	1
##	69	8	Male	23	2	60	depress	37.0000000	1
##	70	13	Male	21	1	70	depress	50.0000000	1
##	71	14	Male	23	2	72	depress	39.0000000	1
##	72	1	Male	19	1	82	depress	44.0000000	1
##	73	15	Male	23	1	79	depress	47.0000000	1
##	74	7	Male	19	1	80	depress	38.0000000	1
##	75	2	Male	21	2	90	depress	50.0000000	1
##	76	27	Female	20	1	56	depress	45.0000000	1
##	77	25	Female	24	1	53	depress	42.0000000	1
##	78	19	Female	27	1	59	depress	49.0000000	1
##	79	18	Female	23	2	64	depress	39.0000000	1

## 80	23	Female	22	1	63	depress	39.0000000	1
## 81	21	Female	46	1	64	depress	44.0000000	1
## 82	26	Female	19	2	63	depress	43.0000000	1
## 83	29	Female	22	1	67	depress	33.0000000	1
## 84	17	Female	37	1	71	depress	39.0000000	1
## 85	20	Female	32	2	73	depress	47.0000000	1
## 86	28	Female	30	2	80	depress	38.0000000	1
## 87	22	Female	25	2	83	depress	45.0000000	1
## 88	24	Female	21	2	85	depress	50.0000000	1
## 89	16	Female	45	2	78	depress	45.0000000	1
## 90	30	Female	21	2	84	depress	34.0000000	1
## 91	4	Male	23	2	52	fost	48.0000000	2
## 92	10	Male	21	2	55	fost	45.0000000	2
## 93	9	Male	25	1	58	fost	39.0000000	2
## 94	3	Male	30	1	60	fost	42.0000000	2
## 95	12	Male	45	2	58	fost	45.0000000	2
## 96	11	Male	22	1	62	fost	40.0000000	2
## 97	6	Male	22	2	59	fost	33.0000000	2
## 98	5	Male	26	1	70	fost	37.0000000	2
## 99	8	Male	23	2	60	fost	40.0000000	2
## 100	13	Male	21	1	70	fost	45.0000000	2
## 101	14	Male	23	2	72	fost	37.0000000	2
## 102	1	Male	19	1	82	fost	28.0000000	2
## 103	15	Male	23	1	79	fost	35.0000000	2
## 104	7	Male	19	1	80	fost	32.0000000	2
## 105	2	Male	21	2	90	fost	36.0000000	2
## 106	27	Female	20	1	56	fost	40.0000000	2
## 107	25	Female	24	1	53	fost	37.0000000	2
## 108	19	Female	27	1	59	fost	41.0000000	2
## 109	18	Female	23	2	64	fost	39.0000000	2
## 110	23	Female	22	1	63	fost	31.0000000	2
## 111	21	Female	46	1	64	fost	40.0000000	2
## 112	26	Female	19	2	63	fost	38.0000000	2
## 113	29	Female	22	1	67	fost	38.0000000	2
## 114	17	Female	37	1	71	fost	40.0000000	2
## 115	20	Female	32	2	73	fost	36.0000000	2
## 116	28	Female	30	2	80	fost	40.0000000	2
## 117	22	Female	25	2	83	fost	28.0000000	2
## 118	24	Female	21	2	85	fost	29.0000000	2
## 119	16	Female	45	2	78	fost	30.0000000	2
## 120	30	Female	21	2	84	fost	36.0000000	2
## 121	4	Male	23	2	52	confid	16.0000000	2
## 122	10	Male	21	2	55	confid	15.0000000	2
## 123	9	Male	25	1	58	confid	18.0000000	2
## 124	3	Male	30	1	60	confid	16.0000000	2
## 125	12	Male	45	2	58	confid	16.0000000	2
## 126	11	Male	22	1	62	confid	20.0000000	2
## 127	6	Male	22	2	59	confid	22.0000000	2
## 128	5	Male	26	1	70	confid	20.0000000	2
## 129	8	Male	23	2	60	confid	23.0000000	2
## 130	13	Male	21	1	70	confid	25.0000000	2
## 131	14	Male	23	2	72	confid	27.0000000	2
## 132	1	Male	19	1	82	confid	25.0000000	2
## 133	15	Male	23	1	79	confid	26.0000000	2

##	134	7	Male	19	1	80	confid	28.0000000	2
##	135	2	Male	21	2	90	confid	30.0000000	2
##	136	27	Female	20	1	56	confid	14.0000000	2
##	137	25	Female	24	1	53	confid	14.0000000	2
##	138	19	Female	27	1	59	confid	13.0000000	2
##	139	18	Female	23	2	64	confid	20.0000000	2
##	140	23	Female	22	1	63	confid	18.0000000	2
##	141	21	Female	46	1	64	confid	19.0000000	2
##	142	26	Female	19	2	63	confid	20.0000000	2
##	143	29	Female	22	1	67	confid	22.0000000	2
##	144	17	Female	37	1	71	confid	22.0000000	2
##	145	20	Female	32	2	73	confid	26.0000000	2
##	146	28	Female	30	2	80	confid	28.0000000	2
##	147	22	Female	25	2	83	confid	28.0000000	2
##	148	24	Female	21	2	85	confid	20.0000000	2
##	149	16	Female	45	2	78	confid	35.0000000	2
##	150	30	Female	21	2	84	confid	30.0000000	2
##	151	4	Male	23	2	52	depress	44.0000000	2
##	152	10	Male	21	2	55	depress	42.0000000	2
##	153	9	Male	25	1	58	depress	40.0000000	2
##	154	3	Male	30	1	60	depress	43.0000000	2
##	155	12	Male	45	2	58	depress	45.0000000	2
##	156	11	Male	22	1	62	depress	42.0000000	2
##	157	6	Male	22	2	59	depress	36.0000000	2
##	158	5	Male	26	1	70	depress	47.0000000	2
##	159	8	Male	23	2	60	depress	37.0000000	2
##	160	13	Male	21	1	70	depress	48.0000000	2
##	161	14	Male	23	2	72	depress	36.0000000	2
##	162	1	Male	19	1	82	depress	43.0000000	2
##	163	15	Male	23	1	79	depress	47.0000000	2
##	164	7	Male	19	1	80	depress	35.0000000	2
##	165	2	Male	21	2	90	depress	47.0000000	2
##	166	27	Female	20	1	56	depress	44.0000000	2
##	167	25	Female	24	1	53	depress	40.0000000	2
##	168	19	Female	27	1	59	depress	49.0000000	2
##	169	18	Female	23	2	64	depress	30.0000000	2
##	170	23	Female	22	1	63	depress	38.0000000	2
##	171	21	Female	46	1	64	depress	44.0000000	2
##	172	26	Female	19	2	63	depress	39.0000000	2
##	173	29	Female	22	1	67	depress	33.0000000	2
##	174	17	Female	37	1	71	depress	40.0000000	2
##	175	20	Female	32	2	73	depress	45.0000000	2
##	176	28	Female	30	2	80	depress	30.0000000	2
##	177	22	Female	25	2	83	depress	40.0000000	2
##	178	24	Female	21	2	85	depress	48.0000000	2
##	179	16	Female	45	2	78	depress	40.0000000	2
##	180	30	Female	21	2	84	depress	30.0000000	2
##	181	4	Male	23	2	52	fost	45.0000000	3
##	182	10	Male	21	2	55	fost	44.0000000	3
##	183	9	Male	25	1	58	fost	36.0000000	3
##	184	3	Male	30	1	60	fost	41.0000000	3
##	185	12	Male	45	2	58	fost	43.0000000	3
##	186	11	Male	22	1	62	fost	39.0000000	3
##	187	6	Male	22	2	59	fost	32.0000000	3

##	188	5	Male	26	1	70	fost	32.0000000	3
##	189	8	Male	23	2	60	fost	40.0000000	3
##	190	13	Male	21	1	70	fost	46.0000000	3
##	191	14	Male	23	2	72	fost	32.0000000	3
##	192	1	Male	19	1	82	fost	23.0000000	3
##	193	15	Male	23	1	79	fost	35.0000000	3
##	194	7	Male	19	1	80	fost	30.0000000	3
##	195	2	Male	21	2	90	fost	34.0000000	3
##	196	27	Female	20	1	56	fost	38.0000000	3
##	197	25	Female	24	1	53	fost	35.0000000	3
##	198	19	Female	27	1	59	fost	40.0000000	3
##	199	18	Female	23	2	64	fost	34.0000000	3
##	200	23	Female	22	1	63	fost	32.0000000	3
##	201	21	Female	46	1	64	fost	38.0000000	3
##	202	26	Female	19	2	63	fost	36.0000000	3
##	203	29	Female	22	1	67	fost	36.0000000	3
##	204	17	Female	37	1	71	fost	40.0000000	3
##	205	20	Female	32	2	73	fost	34.0000000	3
##	206	28	Female	30	2	80	fost	37.0000000	3
##	207	22	Female	25	2	83	fost	25.0000000	3
##	208	24	Female	21	2	85	fost	25.0000000	3
##	209	16	Female	45	2	78	fost	25.0000000	3
##	210	30	Female	21	2	84	fost	30.0000000	3
##	211	4	Male	23	2	52	confid	14.0000000	3
##	212	10	Male	21	2	55	confid	18.0000000	3
##	213	9	Male	25	1	58	confid	19.0000000	3
##	214	3	Male	30	1	60	confid	20.0000000	3
##	215	12	Male	45	2	58	confid	20.0000000	3
##	216	11	Male	22	1	62	confid	22.0000000	3
##	217	6	Male	22	2	59	confid	23.0000000	3
##	218	5	Male	26	1	70	confid	26.0000000	3
##	219	8	Male	23	2	60	confid	26.0000000	3
##	220	13	Male	21	1	70	confid	27.0000000	3
##	221	14	Male	23	2	72	confid	29.0000000	3
##	222	1	Male	19	1	82	confid	30.0000000	3
##	223	15	Male	23	1	79	confid	30.0000000	3
##	224	7	Male	19	1	80	confid	32.0000000	3
##	225	2	Male	21	2	90	confid	34.0000000	3
##	226	27	Female	20	1	56	confid	18.0000000	3
##	227	25	Female	24	1	53	confid	19.0000000	3
##	228	19	Female	27	1	59	confid	20.0000000	3
##	229	18	Female	23	2	64	confid	22.0000000	3
##	230	23	Female	22	1	63	confid	22.0000000	3
##	231	21	Female	46	1	64	confid	23.0000000	3
##	232	26	Female	19	2	63	confid	23.0000000	3
##	233	29	Female	22	1	67	confid	26.0000000	3
##	234	17	Female	37	1	71	confid	27.0000000	3
##	235	20	Female	32	2	73	confid	28.0000000	3
##	236	28	Female	30	2	80	confid	29.0000000	3
##	237	22	Female	25	2	83	confid	30.0000000	3
##	238	24	Female	21	2	85	confid	30.0000000	3
##	239	16	Female	45	2	78	confid	32.0000000	3
##	240	30	Female	21	2	84	confid	32.0000000	3
##	241	4	Male	23	2	52	depress	40.0000000	3

##	242	10	Male	21	2	55	depress	40.0000000	3
##	243	9	Male	25	1	58	depress	38.0000000	3
##	244	3	Male	30	1	60	depress	43.0000000	3
##	245	12	Male	45	2	58	depress	43.0000000	3
##	246	11	Male	22	1	62	depress	38.0000000	3
##	247	6	Male	22	2	59	depress	35.0000000	3
##	248	5	Male	26	1	70	depress	42.0000000	3
##	249	8	Male	23	2	60	depress	35.0000000	3
##	250	13	Male	21	1	70	depress	46.0000000	3
##	251	14	Male	23	2	72	depress	34.0000000	3
##	252	1	Male	19	1	82	depress	40.0000000	3
##	253	15	Male	23	1	79	depress	47.0000000	3
##	254	7	Male	19	1	80	depress	35.0000000	3
##	255	2	Male	21	2	90	depress	45.0000000	3
##	256	27	Female	20	1	56	depress	40.0000000	3
##	257	25	Female	24	1	53	depress	39.0000000	3
##	258	19	Female	27	1	59	depress	44.0000000	3
##	259	18	Female	23	2	64	depress	30.0000000	3
##	260	23	Female	22	1	63	depress	36.0000000	3
##	261	21	Female	46	1	64	depress	44.0000000	3
##	262	26	Female	19	2	63	depress	37.0000000	3
##	263	29	Female	22	1	67	depress	32.0000000	3
##	264	17	Female	37	1	71	depress	40.0000000	3
##	265	20	Female	32	2	73	depress	42.0000000	3
##	266	28	Female	30	2	80	depress	29.0000000	3
##	267	22	Female	25	2	83	depress	38.0000000	3
##	268	24	Female	21	2	85	depress	50.0000000	3
##	269	16	Female	45	2	78	depress	42.0000000	3
##	270	30	Female	21	2	84	depress	32.0000000	3
##	271	4	Male	23	2	52	mah_	0.5699842	1
##	272	10	Male	21	2	55	mah_	1.6594031	1
##	273	9	Male	25	1	58	mah_	3.5404715	1
##	274	3	Male	30	1	60	mah_	2.4542143	1
##	275	12	Male	45	2	58	mah_	0.9443036	1
##	276	11	Male	22	1	62	mah_	1.6257058	1
##	277	6	Male	22	2	59	mah_	4.1744717	1
##	278	5	Male	26	1	70	mah_	1.0261059	1
##	279	8	Male	23	2	60	mah_	1.7053103	1
##	280	13	Male	21	1	70	mah_	3.0873214	1
##	281	14	Male	23	2	72	mah_	2.9140163	1
##	282	1	Male	19	1	82	mah_	0.3469978	1
##	283	15	Male	23	1	79	mah_	1.5886241	1
##	284	7	Male	19	1	80	mah_	1.5076582	1
##	285	2	Male	21	2	90	mah_	10.2401804	1
##	286	27	Female	20	1	56	mah_	1.1776467	1
##	287	25	Female	24	1	53	mah_	1.0564668	1
##	288	19	Female	27	1	59	mah_	3.8748910	1
##	289	18	Female	23	2	64	mah_	2.7101641	1
##	290	23	Female	22	1	63	mah_	3.5488594	1
##	291	21	Female	46	1	64	mah_	0.5007192	1
##	292	26	Female	19	2	63	mah_	1.4739118	1
##	293	29	Female	22	1	67	mah_	9.1295758	1
##	294	17	Female	37	1	71	mah_	6.2065842	1
##	295	20	Female	32	2	73	mah_	1.7190981	1

##	296	28	Female	30	2	80	mah_	1.5015533	1
##	297	22	Female	25	2	83	mah_	1.9240376	1
##	298	24	Female	21	2	85	mah_	7.5576411	1
##	299	16	Female	45	2	78	mah_	1.1884922	1
##	300	30	Female	21	2	84	mah_	6.0455901	1
##	301	4	Male	23	2	52	DepTgp	0.0000000	1
##	302	10	Male	21	2	55	DepTgp	0.0000000	1
##	303	9	Male	25	1	58	DepTgp	0.0000000	1
##	304	3	Male	30	1	60	DepTgp	0.0000000	1
##	305	12	Male	45	2	58	DepTgp	0.0000000	1
##	306	11	Male	22	1	62	DepTgp	0.0000000	1
##	307	6	Male	22	2	59	DepTgp	0.0000000	1
##	308	5	Male	26	1	70	DepTgp	1.0000000	1
##	309	8	Male	23	2	60	DepTgp	0.0000000	1
##	310	13	Male	21	1	70	DepTgp	1.0000000	1
##	311	14	Male	23	2	72	DepTgp	0.0000000	1
##	312	1	Male	19	1	82	DepTgp	0.0000000	1
##	313	15	Male	23	1	79	DepTgp	1.0000000	1
##	314	7	Male	19	1	80	DepTgp	0.0000000	1
##	315	2	Male	21	2	90	DepTgp	1.0000000	1
##	316	27	Female	20	1	56	DepTgp	1.0000000	1
##	317	25	Female	24	1	53	DepTgp	0.0000000	1
##	318	19	Female	27	1	59	DepTgp	1.0000000	1
##	319	18	Female	23	2	64	DepTgp	0.0000000	1
##	320	23	Female	22	1	63	DepTgp	0.0000000	1
##	321	21	Female	46	1	64	DepTgp	0.0000000	1
##	322	26	Female	19	2	63	DepTgp	0.0000000	1
##	323	29	Female	22	1	67	DepTgp	0.0000000	1
##	324	17	Female	37	1	71	DepTgp	0.0000000	1
##	325	20	Female	32	2	73	DepTgp	1.0000000	1
##	326	28	Female	30	2	80	DepTgp	0.0000000	1
##	327	22	Female	25	2	83	DepTgp	1.0000000	1
##	328	24	Female	21	2	85	DepTgp	1.0000000	1
##	329	16	Female	45	2	78	DepTgp	1.0000000	1
##	330	30	Female	21	2	84	DepTgp	0.0000000	1
##	331	4	Male	23	2	52	DepTGp	0.0000000	2
##	332	10	Male	21	2	55	DepTGp	0.0000000	2
##	333	9	Male	25	1	58	DepTGp	0.0000000	2
##	334	3	Male	30	1	60	DepTGp	0.0000000	2
##	335	12	Male	45	2	58	DepTGp	1.0000000	2
##	336	11	Male	22	1	62	DepTGp	0.0000000	2
##	337	6	Male	22	2	59	DepTGp	0.0000000	2
##	338	5	Male	26	1	70	DepTGp	1.0000000	2
##	339	8	Male	23	2	60	DepTGp	0.0000000	2
##	340	13	Male	21	1	70	DepTGp	1.0000000	2
##	341	14	Male	23	2	72	DepTGp	0.0000000	2
##	342	1	Male	19	1	82	DepTGp	0.0000000	2
##	343	15	Male	23	1	79	DepTGp	1.0000000	2
##	344	7	Male	19	1	80	DepTGp	0.0000000	2
##	345	2	Male	21	2	90	DepTGp	1.0000000	2
##	346	27	Female	20	1	56	DepTGp	0.0000000	2
##	347	25	Female	24	1	53	DepTGp	0.0000000	2
##	348	19	Female	27	1	59	DepTGp	1.0000000	2
##	349	18	Female	23	2	64	DepTGp	0.0000000	2

```

## 350 23 Female 22 1 63 DepTGp 0.000000 2
## 351 21 Female 46 1 64 DepTGp 0.000000 2
## 352 26 Female 19 2 63 DepTGp 0.000000 2
## 353 29 Female 22 1 67 DepTGp 0.000000 2
## 354 17 Female 37 1 71 DepTGp 0.000000 2
## 355 20 Female 32 2 73 DepTGp 1.000000 2
## 356 28 Female 30 2 80 DepTGp 0.000000 2
## 357 22 Female 25 2 83 DepTGp 0.000000 2
## 358 24 Female 21 2 85 DepTGp 1.000000 2
## 359 16 Female 45 2 78 DepTGp 0.000000 2
## 360 30 Female 21 2 84 DepTGp 0.000000 2
## 361 4 Male 23 2 52 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 362 10 Male 21 2 55 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 363 9 Male 25 1 58 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 364 3 Male 30 1 60 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 365 12 Male 45 2 58 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 366 11 Male 22 1 62 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 367 6 Male 22 2 59 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 368 5 Male 26 1 70 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 369 8 Male 23 2 60 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 370 13 Male 21 1 70 DepTgp 1.000000 3
## 371 14 Male 23 2 72 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 372 1 Male 19 1 82 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 373 15 Male 23 1 79 DepTgp 1.000000 3
## 374 7 Male 19 1 80 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 375 2 Male 21 2 90 DepTgp 1.000000 3
## 376 27 Female 20 1 56 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 377 25 Female 24 1 53 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 378 19 Female 27 1 59 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 379 18 Female 23 2 64 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 380 23 Female 22 1 63 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 381 21 Female 46 1 64 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 382 26 Female 19 2 63 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 383 29 Female 22 1 67 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 384 17 Female 37 1 71 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 385 20 Female 32 2 73 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 386 28 Female 30 2 80 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 387 22 Female 25 2 83 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 388 24 Female 21 2 85 DepTgp 1.000000 3
## 389 16 Female 45 2 78 DepTgp 0.000000 3
## 390 30 Female 21 2 84 DepTgp 0.000000 3

```

We are mutating two variables. Firstly, we are extracting any number from the `colName` variable and placing that into a new variable called `time` with `parse_number`, then we are removing all digits from `colName` and overwriting it using `gsub`. I like this output for now, so we are going to save it, since this data is more like the data I want, I'm overwriting `eData_tall`.

```

eData_tall <- eData %>%
  gather(colName, value, matches("[123]")) %>%
  mutate(time = parse_number(colName),
         colName = gsub("[[:digit:]]", "", colName))

```

```

## Warning: attributes are not identical across measure variables;
## they will be dropped

```

Because the data are in such a long format now, such that even different types of observations are in one

column (value), made distinct by the information in the colName variable, we can actually plot them all in one ggplot command!

```
eData_tall %>%
  ggplot(aes(x=value)) +
  geom_histogram() +
  facet_wrap(~colName)
```

```
## `stat_bin()` using `bins = 30`. Pick better value with `binwidth`.
```


Look at that, suddenly we have a histogram for each of the variables! What we did there was “Take the data in eData_tall and plot value on the x-axis, make histograms of that, and create different facets (panels) using the information in colName”. Now we also see that apparently there was a naming inconsistency with the DepTgp variables, where one was typed as Gp instead of gp. We will fix that before we continue.

```
eData_tall <- eData %>%
  gather(colName, value, matches("[123]")) %>%
  mutate(time = parse_number(colName),
         colName = gsub("[:digit:]", "", colName),
         colName = gsub("Gp", "gp", colName, ignore.case = FALSE))
```

```
## Warning: attributes are not identical across measure variables;
## they will be dropped
```

I’ve added another line to our mutate function, saying to replace any instance of “Gp”, and “gp” and to make sure to do this as case sensitive. Let’s see if our plot looks better now:

```
eData_tall %>%
  ggplot(aes(x=value)) +
  geom_histogram() +
  facet_wrap(~colName)
```

```
## `stat_bin()` using `bins = 30`. Pick better value with `binwidth`.
```


We can build more on that, because we also have the `time` variable, we can create a facet grid with histograms for each variable at each timepoint very easily

```
eData_tall %>%
  ggplot(aes(x=value)) +
  geom_histogram() +
  facet_grid(colName~time)
```

```
## `stat_bin()` using `bins = 30`. Pick better value with `binwidth`.
```


I think that's pretty neat. We can do that because the data is in long format, and everything is contained in just some few columns, and ggplot can therefore make some nice plots out of, rather than having to tell it about the 5 different columns the data would otherwise be in (one for each variable). Distribution plots might not be the most interesting though, let's look at a plot more similar like the one we did before, scatter plot with a regression line.

The basic's are pretty much the same as above:

```
eData_tall %>%
  ggplot(aes(x=time, y=value)) +
  geom_jitter() +
  geom_smooth(method = "lm") +
  facet_wrap(~colName)
```

```
## `geom_smooth()` using formula 'y ~ x'
```


That's looking much as expected! And we can see that `mah_` only has observations at *one* timepoint, so you would not be able to fit a regression line with that. It's no matter for us now. Since we are interested to have a look across time, we might as well omit `mah_` from the plot. We want the data to remain in the main data, but just not to plot it.

```
eData_tall %>%
  filter( colName != "mah_" ) %>%
  ggplot(aes(x=time, y=value)) +
  geom_jitter() +
  geom_smooth(method = "lm") +
  facet_wrap(~colName)

## `geom_smooth()` using formula 'y ~ x'
```


Now, we added a filter before we did `ggplot`. Here we are going “Take `eData_tall` and filter away any rows where the value in `colName` is `mah_`, then make this `ggplot`”. `DepTgp` is showing some odd behaviour though. It only has values of 0 and 1, and here indicates belonging to a treatment group or not. In R, we would call that variable a logical, i.e. it is a variable indicating if some statement is TRUE (1) or FALSE (0). A standard regression makes no sense in this case. Let’s also filter away these, as they are not interesting here, just like we did with `mah_`.

```
eData_tall %>%
  filter( ! colName %in% c("mah_", "DepTgp")) %>%
  ggplot(aes(x=time, y=value)) +
  geom_jitter() +
  geom_smooth(method = "lm") +
  facet_wrap(~colName)
```

`geom_smooth()` using formula 'y ~ x'

The `filter` now looks a little different than before. Rather than a `!=` (not equal to), we are using `%in%` and negating that (!) in front of the statement. `%in%` is a nice matching shortcut in R, that is vectorised. What that means is that rather than just taking one value to match against (like `!=` or `==`), it can take a series of values to match against. In this case we are going “Take `eData_tall` and filter away any rows where the value in `colName` is either `mah_` or `DepTgp`, then make this `ggplot`”.

Those plots are starting to look very nice. Let us also add some spaghetti in the background. By that I mean, let’s connect the subject data points with lines, so we can see the individual trends in the background of the regression. This should also give us an idea whether there are datapoints that behave oddly over time.

```
eData_tall %>%
  filter( ! colName %in% c("mah_", "DepTgp")) %>%
  ggplot(aes(x=time, y=value)) +
  geom_jitter() +
  geom_line(aes(group=id)) +
  geom_smooth(method = "lm") +
  facet_wrap(~colName)
```

```
## `geom_smooth()` using formula 'y ~ x'
```


That is looking very odd. The points and the lines are not connecting. That is because we are using `geom_jitter`, which generates a little random noise for us so the dots don't plot on top of each other and in very very straight lines. But this happens independently from `geom_line`, so the dots and lines don't know where they should connect.

We can fix that, and I'll break the process down, hopefully to make it understandable. First, let's replace `geom_jitter` with `geom_point` and see what happens.

```
eData_tall %>%
  filter(! colName %in% c("mah_", "DepTgp")) %>%
  ggplot(aes(x=time, y=value)) +
  geom_point() +
  geom_line(aes(group=id)) +
  geom_smooth(method = "lm") +
  facet_wrap(~colName)
```

```
## `geom_smooth()` using formula 'y ~ x'
```


The dots and lines are connecting, good. Overplotting in this case is actually not too bad, in many cases like this, I'd leave it be. But, I mostly have data with many more points, and so I need to find a way to reduce overplotting.

We will be using the ggplot2's function `position_dodge` to introduce noise to both the lines and the points. We will also need to make sure both the lines and the dots have the correct group setting, letting ggplot know that lines and dots are grouped by `id`, meaning that data with the same values in `id` belong together.

```
eData_tall %>%
  filter( ! colName %in% c("mah_", "DepTgp")) %>%
  ggplot(aes(x=time, y=value)) +
  geom_point(aes(group=id), position = position_dodge(width=.5)) +
  geom_line(aes(group=id), position = position_dodge(width=.5)) +
  geom_smooth(method = "lm") +
  facet_wrap(~colName)
```

```
## `geom_smooth()` using formula 'y ~ x'
```


See, now there is a little more space between the points so you can see them all, but everything still connects correctly. The lines and points are a little too domineering, so let's reduce their opacity/transparency, by reducing the `alpha` setting for those two geoms.

```
dodge <- position_dodge(width = .5)
eData_tall %>%
  filter(! colName %in% c("mah_", "DepTgp")) %>%
  ggplot(aes(x=time, y=value)) +
  geom_line(aes(group=id), position = dodge, alpha = .2) +
  geom_point(aes(group=id), position = dodge, alpha = .2) +
  geom_smooth(method = "lm") +
  facet_wrap(~colName)
```

```
## `geom_smooth()` using formula 'y ~ x'
```


When we adjust the `alpha`, we can also see that there still is some overplotting. This is because we cannot create noise in the y-axis, that would be akin to data-manipulation, we should not enter noise in the observed measurements. But the `alpha` helps us see that, and now the regression line is a little more obvious too.

The last thing for today, is changing the regression lines and CI band colour, to make it “pop” more.

```
dodge <- position_dodge(width = .5)
eData_tall %>%
  filter(! colName %in% c("mah_", "DepTgp")) %>%
  ggplot(aes(x=time, y=value)) +
  geom_line(aes(group=id), position = dodge, alpha = .2) +
  geom_point(aes(group=id), position = dodge, alpha = .2) +
  geom_smooth(method = "lm", colour = "forestgreen", fill = "forestgreen") +
  facet_wrap(~colName)
```

```
## `geom_smooth()` using formula 'y ~ x'
```


In this case, altering the colour is very easy, because we set the colour (line) and fill (CI band) to be a single value (not within aes). By setting the colour like this, all panels get the same. We could also use the `colName` variable to give each panel it's own colour.

```
dodge <- position_dodge(width = .5)
eData_tall %>%
  filter(! colName %in% c("mah_", "DepTgp")) %>%
  ggplot(aes(x=time, y=value)) +
  geom_line(aes(group=id), position = dodge, alpha = .2) +
  geom_point(aes(group=id), position = dodge, alpha = .2) +
  geom_smooth(method = "lm", show.legend = FALSE,
             aes(colour=colName, fill=colName)) +
  facet_wrap(~colName)
```

```
## `geom_smooth()` using formula 'y ~ x'
```


that is pretty neat, right?

That's all for this time. We've explored more plots, and ways to change the data, so it becomes easy to plot in this faceted way.

Next time, we will be working on changing factors and factor levels both to make the data correctly portray what it should, and also to help us make our plots meaningful.